

25th NATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON PLANTATION CROPS

Building Smart & Resilient Farming and Systems Approaches
for Prosperity in Plantation Crops Sector

December 12-14, 2023

ABSTRACTS

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Abstracts

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Effect of biopriming with microbial inoculants on seed germination, and seedling growth of large Cardamom (*Amomum subulatum* Roxb.)

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ABSTRACT

Large cardamom (*Amomum subulatum* Roxb.) an important spice crop grown in Sikkim Himalayas and in NE region is generally propagated by vegetative methods. Continuous vegetative propagation may lead to narrowing down of genetic variability. For any successful breeding programme, genetic diversity of germplasm is an important prerequisite. Seed priming is a pre-sowing treatment that allows seeds to germinate more proficiently. Biopriming is the process where seeds are hydrated and treated with microbial inoculants. In the present study, effect of biopriming with microbial inoculants on seed germination and seedling growth of large cardamom was investigated. Various microbial inoculants like baker's yeast, commercial formulation of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (SK - Pseudo), *Bacillus megaterium* (SK - PSB), *Azotobacter* + Phosphate Solubilising Bacteria + K Mobiliser (SK Bio-NPK) were tested. Seeds were soaked in sugar solution (0.5%) containing 1 % microbial inoculants (1×10^8 cfu/ml) for five days and sown on seed beds. The seeds were also soaked in sugar solution (0.5%), 25.0 % cow urine solution (standard treatment) and in water (control) for 5 days. The experiment was conducted in open condition and also in poly house and in each treatment 3 seed beds were raised at a sowing rate of 200 seeds per bed. Seed germination started early in the polyhouse, and it was 47 days ahead of the seeds sown in open conditions. Under polyhouse, maximum germination (38.5 %) was recorded in treatment with *Azotobacter* + PSB + K-Mobiliser, whereas, it was 34.0% in open conditions. The treatment with *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* were on par with the standard cow urine treatment. The biometric parameters of plants showed that the treatment with *Azotobacter*+PSB+ K-Mobiliser had the highest shoot length, no of leaves, root length and vigour index which was statistically significant to all other treatments followed by biopriming with yeast, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Bacillus megaterium* and standard treatment. Thus, it is evident from the present study that biopriming of large cardamom seeds with microbial inoculants can significantly enhance seed germination and seedling growth. The overall performance can further be enhanced in poly house condition. The seedlings are transferred to secondary poly bags for further observations and also to subsequently evaluate their performance under field conditions.

Key words: Large Cardamom, Seed Germination, Biopriming, Microbial Inoculants

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